

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS – VOL. 14 (2021)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2021, vol. 14

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

TECHNOLOGY AS A REFLECTION OF A SOCIETY: THE CASE OF DATAFICATION AND SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS

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Abstract

The article critically questions popular predictions about how technology (the Internet and especially social media) change society. It focuses firstly on the relation between society and technology in order to explain why technological changes and corresponding social problems are foremost a reflection of the priorities of a culture. The article presents some major shifts (information, datafication) which are the foundation of current transformations. In the second part of the article, the attention shifts towards social media platforms. The actual usage of social media promotes the cultural logic of branding the self. Nowadays, visibility and attention have become the driving force of most social media users. The paper highlights potential obstacles regarding modern usage of social media. The power of the citizens to choose what kind of information best suits them is a welcome novelty but it also might confront us with problematic scenarios. That is to say social media optimism is based mainly on the techno-deterministic viewpoint of empowering technology. Much more attention has to be placed on technology in the sense of discovering what values, competences and scenarios are inscribed into actual usages of technology in order to fully understand how and why is technology implicated in social relations and human knowledge, and in what sense our praxeology of everyday life is technologically driven.

Key words: technology, information, datafication, social network sites, communication

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Introduction: technologies as a “natural phenomenon”

The aim of the article is the problematization and deconstruction of “mythological” perceptions within current understandings of modern technologies. It is quite typical for our time to understand communication technologies as an undoubted transformative force and to attach various “capabilities” to the very technologies. The unquestionability of such an idea is ideologically motivated and widely presented in popular media coverage. It is also reproduced as a common-sense background in everyday conversation. The starting point of the article is firstly to analyze the complexity of the relationship between technology and society and to acknowledge the social construction of technologies. Technologies are not “born” by themselves; they are invented and disseminated by individuals and social groups upon specific social conditions. Socio-cultural context to a great extent determines motivations for what to develop and what kind of “instructions for use” are most socially preferable. The sociality of technologies is thus reflected at the level of selection of technology and upon the wider social atmosphere and values typical for a specific period of time. The scientific approach named social construction of technology (SCOT)¹ acknowledges that “the

¹ Social construction of technologies (abb. SCOT) (wikipedia/ Social construction of technology) is a subfield of Science and technology studies or science, technology and society studies (both abbreviated STS (wikipedia/Science and technology studies). STS are the study of how society, politics, and culture affect scientific research and technological innovation, and how these, in turn, affect society, politics and culture. Another important constructivist approach that avoids essentialist explanations of events or innovations is Actor-network theory (abb. ANT) (wikipedia/ Actor-network theory). Classical media and communication studies from 1920 onward usually analyzed “effects” of print, broadcasting, and cinema on audiences’ opinions, attitudes, values, and behavior; although this work focused mainly on media content, it also grew out of concerns that the channels themselves might have some inherent power to influence audiences. Later, studies of “new” information and communication technologies (ICTs) and information society in the 1970s and 80s investigated the “impacts” of computer conferencing, videotex, Usenet groups, and electronic mail technologies on occupational patterns, organizational structure, small group interaction, and individual users. (Lievrouw, 2014: 21). Because sometimes very optimistic in viewing technology as remarkable driving force for social changes, these considerations were to a great extent techno-deterministic. Later on concepts and critiques arising from studies of science, technology, and society (science and technology studies, or STS) came to the forefront in studies of new media and communication technology. The most influential was the social construction of technology (SCOT) approach to the analysis of technology and society. These concepts and frameworks encouraged communication technology researchers to reject technological determinism in favor of a view of technology as socially constructed. (Lievrouw, 2014: 21–22). As Leah A.

developmental process of a technological artifact is described as an alternation of variation and selection. This results in a 'multidirectional' model, in contrast with the linear models used explicitly in many innovation studies and implicitly in much history of technology. Such a multidirectional view is essential to any social constructivist account of technology. Of course, with historical hindsight, it is possible to collapse the multidirectional model on to a simpler linear model; but this misses the thrust of our argument that the 'successful' stages in the development are not the only possible ones." (Pinch, Bijker, 1993: 28). It is important to understand that the evolution of technologies is not unilinear but a highly complex process of different potential directions of which only some are really chosen and subsequently become "successful". Additionally, we must be aware that even in the phase when a certain version of technology is chosen and, upon ideological and marketing discourses, becomes socially accepted as "the right technology" it is up to individuals to decide how to use technologies. Certainly, technologies usually contain "instructions for use" on the level of interaction between the individual and technology. Apart from the technological aspects of usage, it is also a social domain of usage. The actual spectrum of uses is nevertheless dependent upon individuals. When considering usage it is also taken for granted, that the use of information and communication technology (or any other technology) by individuals, organizations, and nations is taken as "the norm" and non-use is perceived as a sign of a deficiency: "Many authors have pointed to the ways in which producers and designers of technology draw on the "I-methodology," using themselves as the paradigm of a user or the singular, undifferentiated user, or users in the plural as a homogeneous group. Including the variety of non-

Lievrouw arguably stresses that kind of reorientation was a huge revolution in considering and looking at the relationship between technology and society: "Consequently, to a great extent the classical 'effects' or 'impacts' viewpoint in new media research gave way to studies with a broadly social constructivist perspective and an emphasis on social shaping, the shared or negotiated meaning of technologies, user studies, and technological systems as products and representations of culture. The question was no longer what communication technologies or media do to people, but rather, how people appropriate, understand, make sense and continuously reconstruct them. Communication technologies - at once resources for and manifestations of communication, meaning, and culture - seemed to epitomize the articulation between the technical and the social." (Lievrouw, 2014: 22).

users also helps to open the way for subtler description and analysis of the multiplicity of users.” (Wyatt, 2003: 77–79).

What is therefore even more important is how we as a society deal with the potentials and affordances given to us by technologies. Let’s enumerate some opportunities which are typical for our time: technologies enable potential opportunities to speed up our communication, to maximize our daily time, to optimize our performance, to develop our multitasking. What is obvious, but usually overlooked is that we are talking about our communication, our performance, our multitasking. It is society that wants to speed up processes, to optimize performances, to enable multitasking: “We now have an abundance of time-saving technologies that are supposed to make our lives easier, and yet our lives feel busier and more stressed than ever. We blame gadgets for the constraints of constant connectivity and yet we turn to those same gadgets for a solution. The belief that machines can be profitably employed to control and manage time has a long history, one that is reflected in contemporary socio-technical scenarios of what automation can be expected to deliver. The argument here is that the contemporary imperative of speed and efficiency has deeper roots than digital technology - it is as much a cultural artefact as it is a technological one. If we feel pressured into optimising our use of time, the priorities and parameters we set ourselves are to blame rather than the machines as such” (King, Gerisch, Rosa, 2019: 5). In other words: we have to look at technology and its popular uses as a specific articulation of society, a specific “embodiment” of society and its dominant motivations. Technologies are therefore the most and foremost a reflection of society. If we want to reflect social problems occurring in our time, we have to analyze technology and society together and critically investigate the social motivations which are “underneath” current debates. It is well described in the following passage written by Judy Wajcman: “the contemporary imperative of speed is as much a cultural artifact as it is a technological one. That if we feel rushed and pressed for time, it’s because of the priorities and parameters we ourselves set rather than the machines per se” (Wajcman, 2016: 194). Judy Wajcman gives us a powerful description, a kind of diagnosis for current problems: “Our age is obsessed with speed: faster cars, faster trains, faster broadband, even speed dating. Speed is sexy, and digital devices are constantly sold to us as efficient, time-saving tools that promote an exciting, action-packed lifestyle” (Wajcman, 2015: 13). Again, speed is sexy

for society, and in line with the obsession to speed up processes, we inevitably understand the evolution of technology and use of technologies through the framework of “speed” as it is the only framework we are able to think through: “We are so immersed in this culture of busyness and hyper-productivity that it’s hard to raise questions about whether speed itself should be the ultimate rationale for innovation” (Wajcman, 2016: 196).

Therefore, the problems occurring in society are not produced by technologies; they are related to social values and motivations individuals wish to fulfil. Technology has in that respect more or less the status of assistance, a kind of technical supply for potential opportunities, but the final decision how and for what reason to use these technological opportunities is nevertheless social.

Ideological backgrounds: “Powerful individuals” and “powerful technology”

It is quite common and popular to present technology as a driving force for social transformation. That kind of presentation of powerful or omnipotent technology is presented in the popular press, it is expressed in everyday conversations among ordinary people, and it is a very frequent manifestation of common sense. Applying this techno-deterministic view is a very “safe” way of thinking about technologies as active and “aggressive” elements. These lines of considerations are too simple an explanation of complex social problems. Nevertheless, technology is always silent, therefore a welcomed “excuse” for social problems: “The most influential common sense assumption about the relationship between technology and society is ‘technological determinism’. Few would explicitly subscribe to this theory, but, as I have indicated, it is pervasive. It has several versions, but in its strongest version, it is the claim that technological innovation is the most important cause of change in society. Key here is the idea that technology impinges on society from the outside, that technical change is autonomous and itself causes social change. That technology is not part of society but a separate, external sphere, so to speak.” (Wajcman, 2015: 27).

The belief or more properly myth that technology has the potential to transform societies has different versions; advocates of this approach see technologies either as “negative” or “positive” vehicles producing some effects. This kind of techno-pessimism and techno-optimism is especially typical when talking about social media. Both assume that

the Internet is the solution to society's problems and that it can perfect society and get rid of the existence of problems. Christian Fuchs points out that the "Internet and social media act as arena of ideological projections of fears and hopes that are associated with moral panics - some argue that they are dangerous spaces that are used by terrorists, rioters, vandals and criminals and therefore needs to be policed with the help of Internet surveillance, whereas others argue that the Internet is a new space of political hope that is at the heart of demonstrations, rebellions, protests and revolutions that struggle for more democracy. What both discourses share is a strong belief in the power of technology independently of society, they mistake societal phenomena (crime, terror, crises, political transformation) to be caused and controllable by technology" (Fuchs, 2015: 18–20). Both versions are techno-deterministic in their consideration of technology as a powerful panacea for social problems. As Fuchs continues: "societal phenomena merely express themselves in communicative and technological spaces; technologies do not cause them. Technological determinism inscribes power into technology; it reduces power to a technologically manageable phenomenon and therefore neglects the interaction of technology and society" (Fuchs, 2015: 20).

We are therefore confronted with various ideas concerning the power of technology and its potential for transforming society. Additionally, the confusion and difficulty of critically approaching the society-technology relationship is accompanied with the popular, usually (neo)liberal understanding of modern individuals. Because we live in a so-called individualistic society, special attention is put on the individual and his or her potentials. The modern individual is absolutely "free" and therefore responsible for his/her success. The media and popular discourses are full of optimistic prophecies concerning the individual. But like every too simplistic explanation, it has also a "dark" side. Namely, it is quite usual in popular media discourse to picture individuals who are fully confident, strong, who know what they are living for. It is a basic frame of modern discourse: individuals and their strengths, their capabilities and opportunities. Nowadays, the power is put fully into the hands of individuals. Life is ours, our happiness is in our own hands. In parallel with these presented "powerful" individuals the picture of "powerful" technology still exists. Both ideas are ideological and are mostly a reflection of (neo)liberal hegemony. Nowadays, individuals are "free" and therefore fully responsible for themselves and their "happiness" and

future engagements in the so-called labour market. Accordingly, technology is quite “free” and responsible for transformations in society. What do we mean by that? It is quite usual for stakeholders, for example in the media, “to blame” technology (algorithms, automatization, artificial intelligence) as a “cause” for firing employees. That kind of one-dimensional and “one-way ticket” explanation sees society and individuals as hostages of technologies. Technologies “just happen” and we have to live with “acceptable losses”, be it in reducing the number of employees, cutting salaries, etc. Technology is used and presented as a cause and as a solution (Praprotnik, 2020: 611).

In the last decade, this empowering force inscribed to technology has become even bigger. What happened? One of the major changes is the growth of social media and activities performed through social media: networking, collaboration, sharing, etc. Social media are not information channels, they are mostly communication channels. They are vehicles for social interaction. At the centre of these networks are individuals (Praprotnik, 2019: 122).

Datafication as a process and as a tool: does size (quantity) really matter?

It is quite common to see technologies as vehicles that revolutionize societies or upgrade society. By all means, we should be sceptical towards totalizing narratives of so-called postindustrial, information and network society. Their techno-optimistic implication is inscribed in the very formulation: information society, network society. The very description of society as postindustrial, information, or network alludes to something radically new happening, as we are entering a “new” phase of society. Such formulations picture dramatic changes in society, and consequently, they anticipate future positive developments within society on the basis of new, revolutionizing, all-empowering technology. We have already been faced with several disappointments regarding the transformative potentials of the Internet, which were inspired by techno-optimism. James Curran, Natalie Fenton and Des Freedman in their book *Misunderstanding the Internet* acknowledge in the same spirit that a decontextualised focus on the technology of the Internet leads to misperceiving its impact. They enumerate different technology-centred predictions about how the Internet would change society, and then present what actually happened. “The Internet did not promote global understanding in the way that had been anticipated because the

Internet came to reflect the inequalities, linguistic division, conflicting values and interests of the real world. The Internet did not spread and rejuvenate democracy in the way that had been promised, partly because authoritarian regimes usually found ways of controlling the Internet, but also because alienation from the political process limited the Internet's emancipatory potential. The Internet did not transform the economy, partly because the underlying dynamics of unequal competition that make for corporate concentration remained unchanged. Lastly, the Internet did not inaugurate a renaissance of journalism; on the contrary, it enabled leading news brands to extend their ascendancy across technologies, while inducing a decline of quality not offset, so far, by new forms of journalism. All four predictions were wrong because they inferred the impact of the Internet from its technology and failed to grasp that the Internet's influence is filtered through the structures and processes of society" (Curran, Fenton, Freedman, 2012: 179). Every optimistic scenario is just a reflection of directing too much attention and strength towards technology. This kind of techno-utopia or techno-optimism expects too much from technology and too little from society. It is a reflection of the already mentioned separation between society and technology which reproduces the idea that a "better" society will evolve as soon as "better" technology emerges.

We can find inspirational texts questioning the power of technology in the past. Theodore Roszak published an illuminating book *The Cult of Information* (1986a), which problematizes the very foundation of modern society. Roszak acknowledges in an interview that "information is becoming a Good word of our time. And it should be purely obvious why that's happening. It's because we are living in the age, when the most powerful element in our culture is the invention of the computer, the research and the development under computer and the computer is an information-processing machine. And if you want to sell a lot of computers in a society you have to convince people that information is terribly important" (Roszak, 1986b). As he continued in an interview for the television programme *Thinking Allowed TV* (Roszak, 1986b), we are giving more and more attention and weight to information as well as broadening the very definitions of information. As a consequence, information is becoming more and more vital for society. As Roszak stressed, some basic distinctions have been obscured, for example information, knowledge, judgement, and wisdom. What is far more central for thinking, for the art of thinking, is the mastery of ideas, because

cultures are based upon ideas (Roszak, 1986b). As Roszak stresses, lots of ideas governing our culture are not based on information, but these ideas are nevertheless important “organizational principle” of our cultural and political life. Roszak presents very familiar example of idea, namely: “All men are created equal”. It is a powerful idea, but there is absolutely no information in this idea. This idea is based upon experience and moral vision. The idea was not done by research. The idea was based rather upon moral insights of generations that have come to find a great sympathy for democratic politics (Roszak, 1986b). As Roszak states in his book: “The power of this familiar idea will not be lost on any of us. From it, generations of legal and philosophical controversy have arisen, political movements and revolutions have taken their course” (Roszak, 1986a: 91). So, what Roszak is suggesting is that master ideas like “All men are created equal” are based on no information whatever and he is using the idea “to emphasize the radical difference between ideas and data which the cult of information has done so much to obscure” (Roszak, 1986a: 91).

As we have been witnessing for last the couple of decades, information has become even more important. Digitalization and especially web-based datafication have turned information and data into the very centre of our interests. Datafication as a process and as a tool has become the “master idea” of our time, employing more and more effort in the optimization and algorithmization of information. It is important to understand that datafication as a process is not only a technological novelty. Datafication as a process of collecting and registering information about almost all everyday mundane processes is a novelty which highlights the basic postulates of how we deal with processes in society, how we understand society and what kind of predictions we are making based on the data we collect. Datafication allows us to analyze society as a whole, not just as a sample as we used to. Because we can analyze far more data, we are able to get a “big picture” with subcategories, trends, niche markets, etc. Big data represent a shift in the way we use information. Instead of collecting data from an intentionally designed sample in order to detect causal relation, we collect all possible data (information) in order to detect correlation. These shifts are important methodological changes. Although we are able to collect enormously interesting insights into processes occurring within society, we are at the same time confronted with difficulties usually labelled as “acceptable losses”. What is different when comparing traditional

statistical searching for causal relations (in terms of independent and dependent variables) and big data analytics? So, for example, correlation is not telling us why something is happening, but it alerts or informs us that something is happening. It is a kind of registering of all manifest processes without being able to explain the dynamics and motivation underlying these processes. Instead of looking for causal relations, we are looking to see what is trending, we are calculating the probability of certain things happening in the future. We use information in new ways such as predictive analysis. The shift is therefore in how we use information and what we are looking for in information. (Mayer-Schonberger and Cukier, 2013; Holmes, 2017). When Nick Couldry problematizes current debates and positive projections upon Big data analytics he is aware of “the huge capacities of computer-based analysis now increasingly influencing science, corporate and governmental agendas” and that “massive computing capacity really is vital to discovering complex patterns in huge datasets, for example in the medical field” (Couldry, 2014: 887). But what he finds problematic are “the claims now being made about what big data can achieve for understanding our world”. (Couldry, 2014: 887).

Nick Couldry is well aware of the problems occurring within such an approach to social processes: “The world too will look different: ‘we will no longer regard our world as a string of happenings that we explain as a natural or social phenomenon, but as a universe comprised essentially of information’ (Mayer-Schonberger and Cukier, 2013: 96, in Couldry, 2014: 888). On the other hand, when the moral consequences of acting on the basis of ‘big data’ arises - for example, arresting people for offences they are predicted to commit but haven’t yet - they back off and say that big data only provide probabilities, not actualities, and worry about ‘fetishizing the output of our [data] analysis’” (Mayer-Schonberger and Cukier, 2013: 151 in Couldry, 2014: 888). So, datafication and using information to detect trends is an entirely different approach from previous scientific approaches. Chris Anderson was obviously well aware of that “reverse” logic when he wrote back in 2008: “It calls for an entirely different approach, one that requires us to lose the tether of data as something that can be visualized in its totality. It forces us to view data mathematically first and establish a context for it later. For instance, Google conquered the advertising world with nothing more than applied mathematics. It didn’t pretend to know anything about the culture and conventions of advertising - it just assumed that

better data, with better analytical tools, would win the day. And Google was right.” (Anderson, 2008). We can say that business models and strategies are changing in line with intensified datafication. The winners in these novel processes are already successful corporate organizations: “Thirdly, the business model of Google and Facebook depends on collecting all the data generated by users’ activities and analysing it to develop personalised profiles that can then be used to micro manage promotional appeals tailored to tap into known preferences and interests” (Murdock, 2017: 29). Shoshana Zuboff arguably acknowledges the inscribed inequality: “Surveillance capitalism operates through unprecedented asymmetries in knowledge and the power that accrues to knowledge. Surveillance capitalists know everything about us, whereas their operations are designed to be unknowable to us. They accumulate vast domains of new knowledge from us, but not for us. They predict our futures for the sake of others’ gain, not ours.” (Zuboff, 2019: ch. 1).

Mark Andrejevic names this new situation as a “big data divide” (Andrejevic, 2014: 1683).

But what Anderson is pointing to is not just marketing and advertising but the transformation of the basic approaches to how to look at a society: how a society is constituted, what makes the society social, and what basic social processes and relations among various individuals and social groups are. Big data analytics is providing simple solutions for complex questions: “This is a world where massive amounts of data and applied mathematics replace every other tool that might be brought to bear. Out with every theory of human behavior, from linguistics to sociology. Forget taxonomy, ontology, and psychology. Who knows why people do what they do? The point is they do it, and we can track and measure it with unprecedented fidelity. With enough data, the numbers speak for themselves. The big target here isn’t advertising, though. It’s science. The scientific method is built around testable hypotheses. These models, for the most part, are systems visualized in the minds of scientists. The models are then tested, and experiments confirm or falsify theoretical models of how the world works. This is the way science has worked for hundreds of years. Scientists are trained to recognize that correlation is not causation, that no conclusions should be drawn simply on the basis of correlation between X and Y (it could just be a coincidence). Instead, you must understand the underlying mechanisms that connect the two. Once you have a

model, you can connect the data sets with confidence. Data without a model is just noise.” (Anderson, 2008). Once we have such a model solely based upon calculating probabilities and correlations, the “sociality” of a world almost disappears, because “sociality” is of no use as an explanatory source. It seems like big data analytics constructs an “explanatory model” by itself. It is not a tool we are using to interpret particular processes within the social world. Big data analytics has become a model for interpreting the social world on the basis of constructing the world. What do we mean by that? By calculating probabilities and trends they generate and construct further processes that they refer to as “probabilities and trends”. Shoshana Zuboff in explaining modern surveillance capitalism goes even further in predicting future processes: “[...] automated machine processes not only know our behavior but also shape our behavior at scale. With this reorientation from knowledge to power, it is no longer enough to automate information flows about us; the goal now is to automate us.” (Zuboff, 2019: ch. 1).

The big data model of calculating trends and probability is becoming a big commercial success within the field of consumption and marketing. Namely, calculating and declaring “what is trending” in society enhances the already established consumption behaviour to the extreme. Although we cannot say that big data analytics is a “false consciousness” or “false definition of the situation” (Merton, 1968: 477) from the very beginning, its model of probability nevertheless functions to some extent as a self-fulfilling prophecy in its consequences. Consumers may think in the following way: “Well, I do not believe absolutely in big data announced trends but I am sure that lots of people believe in big data results and they will act accordingly. Therefore, I have to be smart enough to be in line with trending goods in order not to be the only “fool” that happened to be “outside the trend”. We are talking about the sociopsychological phenomenon of someone “predicting” or expecting something, and this “prediction” or expectation coming true simply because the person believes it will and the person's resulting behaviour aligning to fulfil the belief. An additional driving force or circumstance for this kind of behaviour is a social comparison among individuals as consumers: “To evaluate the Internet's ambiguous effects on consumers, it is necessary only to see a simple point: When millions of consumers simultaneously find themselves with improved opportunities to find goods, they are likely to find themselves of a kind of ‘treadmill’ in which each is continually trying to purchase more

and better, simply in order to keep up with others and with the ever-shifting frame of reference.” (Sunstein, 2006: 209–210). What we are pointing to is the basic frame of what to consume and why to consume. If the individual basic frame is transformed from “how to be a citizen” to “how to be a consumer”, we are dealing with a dramatic transformation of what an individuals might think is important (for him/her, for society...): “But when what matters is the frame set for social comparison, a society focused on better consumer goods will face a serious problem: People will channel far too many resources into the consumption ‘treadmill’, and far too few into goods that are not subject to the treadmill effect, or that would otherwise be far better for society (such as improved protection against crime or environmental pollution, or assistance for poor people).” (Sunstein, 2006: 210).

So, even if we accept the positive novelty of datafication within marketing because “predicting users’ individual attributes and preferences can be used to improve numerous products and services” (Kosinski, Stillwell, Graepel, 2013: 5805) we should be aware of other scenario too: “On the other hand, the predictability of individual attributes from digital records of behavior may have considerable negative implications, because it can easily be applied to large numbers of people without obtaining their individual consent and without them noticing. Commercial companies, governmental institutions, or even one’s Facebook friends could use software to infer attributes such as intelligence, sexual orientation, or political views that an individual may not have intended to share. One can imagine situations in which such predictions, even if incorrect, could pose a threat to an individual’s well-being, freedom, or even life” (Kosinski, Stillwell, Graepel, 2013: 5805).¹

¹ Authors of a study demonstrate the degree to which relatively basic digital records of human behavior can be used to automatically and accurately estimate a wide range of personal attributes that people would typically assume to be private. The study is based on Facebook Likes, a mechanism used by Facebook users to express their positive association with (or “Like”) online content, such as photos, friends’ status updates, Facebook pages of products, sports, musicians, books, restaurants, or popular Web sites. As authors stress: “We show that easily accessible digital records of behavior, Facebook Likes, can be used to automatically and accurately predict a range of highly sensitive personal attributes including: sexual orientation, ethnicity, religious and political views, personality traits, intelligence, happiness, use of addictive substances, parental separation, age, and gender. The analysis presented is based on a dataset of over 58,000 volunteers who

Datafication with its accent on predictive analytics has theoretically different paths of use. It is very likely the tool is going to be used in the old-fashioned way we already know: categorisation and discrimination. In labelling people society discriminates against people. Labels do not reflect “reality”; instead social labelling is the basis for discrimination. By labelling we construct “problematic” individuals; therefore, we are talking about the performative dimension of labelling. By naming a group of people homosexuals, we construct a special group with “special” characteristics, therefore alluding to the “problematic” character of a group. The problem does not lie in individuals, the problem lies in discourse. Datafication with predictive analysis is trying to find patterns and similarities. Datafication as a tool can therefore partly frame what is relevant (at the level of the individual), how to look at the individual or society and what to look at all. Is sexual orientation relevant? For whom? We should be aware of the problematic implications of a process which enables datafication of everyone and everything. Turning individuals into numbers is a process which unproblematically obscures relevant social processes and sets the relevance to datafied “manifest” characteristics (sexual orientation), therefore drawing attention to individual characteristics as an “important” explanatory model. Within such predictive analysis we are once again approaching the already known discriminatory practice of categorization as a basis for discriminating against individuals.

As Couldry acknowledges we are dealing with serious transformations especially within the domain of social sciences: “It does not have as its domain a national population, or even the particular collectivities that might gather online. It builds its population, data-bit by data-bit, through a series of operations that bypass earlier ideas of social interrelations. Its new form of ‘social knowledge’ splits up discourse populations: the groups that could once be talked about as populations for various purposes. It fractures the space of discourse, depicting its data subjects in ways that don’t connect any more with the space of action and thought in which actual individuals think they live; and it stretches the time of discourse, aggregating action fragments from any moment in the

provided their Facebook Likes, detailed demographic profiles, and the results of several psychometric tests.” (Kosinski, Stillwell, Graepel, 2013: 5802).

stream of a person's recorded acts into patterns that bear little relationship to how those people themselves understand the sequence and meaning of their actions. Combine all this and mystify it through the myth of big data - and you risk replacing older ways of talking about the social world that can still be related to social actors with myriad data-strings that lack any elements that connect with how individuals, with recognisable sets of human aims and capabilities, make sense of what they do." (Couldry, 2014: 889). So what is at risk with big data revolution or - as Mayer-Schonberger and Cukier (2013: 96) optimistically claim "an essential enrichment in human comprehension", is the very foundation of what does it mean to be social: "We risk building a social landscape peopled by [...] unwitting data producers, but that are not alive, not at least in the sense we know human beings to be alive." (Couldry, 2014: 888–890). These revolutionary shifts in using information are not without considerations: "Developing a deep understanding of how digital technologies and their capacities for generating, visualising and sharing data are becoming part of our quotidian worlds is an essential step for contemporary social science. It is needed to inform both how we theorise processes of change and intervention in contemporary everyday life, and to contextualise and situate the massive digital data sets that academics, governments and organisations increasingly hope will explain current and predict future societal change and contribute to economic and social development." (Pink, Sumartojo, Lupton, Heyes La Bond, 2017: 1).

The more the technology of algorithms evolves, the more emphasis is put on information per se. Since information has become a "Good word of our time" (cf. Roszak), it is quite obvious why we are placing so much attention on processes (algorithmization, datafication) which are based on information: "Algorithms manage our interactions on social networking sites, highlighting the news of one friend while excluding another's. Algorithms designed to calculate what is "hot" or "trending" or "most discussed" skim the cream from the seemingly boundless chatter that's on offer. Together, these algorithms not only help us find information, they also provide a means to know what there is to know and how to know it, to participate in social and political discourse, and to familiarize ourselves with the publics in which we participate." (Gillespie, 2014: 167).

It seems like we are constantly confronted with technological novelties which "just happen". It would be productive and illuminating

for society to discuss firstly within society (or with ourself) what our greater challenges are and the problems we are dealing with (inequality, labour market, discrimination), and to develop technologies according to these detected inadequacies. Datafication as a current and all-encompassing process is mostly a process of collecting information and making predictions based on the registered information. It is not oriented towards discovering why some processes are happening. It is not a tool for addressing how to solve problems in society. A critical tool lies in society, in “master ideas” as a basic orientation to what matters, what values are important to follow. A critical tool lies in our knowledge, in our motivation and preparedness to cope with our own problems. Maybe we should more actively engage with our master ideas as mentioned by Roszak and let them drive our society. That means engaging technologies in order to fulfil or enhance the framework of our ideas of equality, etc. The proposal of Judy Wajcman quoted above is quite simple but nevertheless very difficult to manage since the process of invention, dissemination and popularization of technologies is shaped by different and to a great extent political and economic factors. “Outer” motivations (=economic, political) of certain groups prevail upon inner motivations and ideas. They are usually political and economic elites who decide what kind of technology is “proper” and “efficient” for society. It is typical for our times that “information management” is put forward in order to present particular interests of elites as common interests: “From acknowledgement that any business organisation ‘depends ultimately on public approval and is therefore faced with the problem of engineering the public’s consent to a program or goal’ (Bernays, 1952: 159 in Webster, 2006: 192) follows a panoply of corporate communications. In the modern business corporation the management of public opinion is an integral element of the overall marketing strategy” (Webster, 2006: 192). The already mentioned “inner” motivations are usually neglected or obscured by “information management”. Jürgen Habermas regards the growth of information management as signalling the decline of the public sphere and Webster arguably acknowledges that “Habermas is undeniably correct in so far as the promotion of propaganda, persuasion and public opinion management does evidence a shift away from the idea of an informed and reasoning public towards an acceptance of the message and manipulation of public opinion by the technicians of public relations” (Webster, 2006: 191). So, in returning to Wajcman, what would be better scenario for society when dealing with technology?

“Now let me be absolutely clear. I am not nostalgic for a more natural, less digitized, past. Neither do I see the emerging slow time movements (whether it’s slow food or mindfulness) as the solution. Rather, I am arguing that we need to be much more discriminating and demanding about the kinds of technologies we want, and the values and purposes they might serve. And this involves redefining genuine inventiveness as not just about speed and novelty, but about challenging the assumptions that permeate our scientific discourse. To put it simply, it means thinking about social problems first and then thinking of technical solutions, rather than the other way around.” (Wajcman, 2016: 197). Shoshana Zuboff (2019: ch.18) has a quite similar conclusion while addressing the problems of surveillance capitalism: “That surveillance capitalism has usurped so many of our rights in these domains is a scandalous abuse of digital capabilities and their once grand promise to democratize knowledge and meet our thwarted needs for effective life. Let there be a digital future, but let it be a human future first.”

What is so revolutionary in/about social media platforms?

We can generally conclude that quite the same techno-optimistic predictions occur every time a new technology emerges. Take the “last example”—we are referring to the social media. Social media are not important only for societies as a whole. They have “revolutionized” the everyday life of individuals too. Social media give individuals opportunities for different ways of organizing life, enabling them a vast field of communication and exploration of potential lifestyle possibilities (Praprotnik, 2019: 123). The basic frame of social media is networking, which has become an important resource for establishing connections, to explore new lifestyles, and to develop the skills needed for successful life planning. Networking is our main organizational principle. We are constantly connected to one another. Manuel Castells (2014) is perhaps best known for popularizing “networking” as a driving force. For Castells, the revolution in ICT has given rise to a new information age, a network society in which labour and capital are replaced by informational networks and knowledge. Manuel Castells briefly summarizes the basic frames of the modern network society in the following manner: “A primary dimension of these changes is what has been labelled the rise of the Me-centered society, or, in sociological terms, the process of individuation, the decline of community understood in terms of space, work, family, and ascription in general. This is not the end of

community, and not the end of place-based interaction, but there is a shift toward the reconstruction of social relationships, including strong cultural and personal ties that could be considered a form of community, on the basis of individual interests, values, and projects” (Castells, 2014: 136–137).

In Castells’ considerations, the magic word is networking as it will revolutionize society as a whole. As in every “almost too perfect” constellation, it is useful to look beyond such seemingly perfectness and - as it usually appears to be - “naturalness”. Why does social media look like such a natural and self-evident modern environment? What happened? Nick Couldry analyzes these kind of processes within the logic of myths: “Calling these different processes ‘myths’ enables us to see an underlying pattern in how, as societies, we make sense of organizing things around assumptions that certain types of information, expertise and knowledge are more valuable than others, and offer us a privileged view on the reality of social life. I say ‘we’ because these myths are not merely an elite production: we are all, potentially, involved in producing these myths through our everyday actions (making ‘myth’ a more useful term, incidentally, than ‘ideology’)” (Couldry, 2014: 885–886). Nick Couldry firstly introduces the myth of the mediated centre “to point to the long history whereby media institutions became increasingly implicated in the languages, practices and organizational logics of whole societies. This myth is what we might call a ‘reserve rationalization’ that makes sense of our organizing our lives around the content flows of media organizations; it tells us that society has a ‘centre’ of value, knowledge and meaning, and that particular institutions, those we call ‘media’, have a privileged role in giving us access to that supposed ‘centre’. Media institutions work hard to sustain that myth, telling us we are all watching, that this programme or event shows ‘what’s going on’ for us as a society.” (Couldry, 2014: 882–885). In an age of social media platforms we are witnessing a new myth, the myth of us: “A new myth about the collectivities we form when we use platforms such as Facebook. An emerging myth of natural collectivity that is particularly seductive, because here traditional media institutions seem to drop out altogether from the picture: the story is focused entirely on what ‘we’ do naturally, when we have the chance to keep in touch with each other, as of course we want to do. Charlotte Brunson and David Morley (1978) had a brilliant phrase for the myth of the mediated centre at its mass media peak in the late 1970s: the ‘nation now’. Today, when Facebook offers to ‘tell the

story of our lives', we have: 'us now'." (Couldry, 2014: 885). The latter will be discussed in detail in this chapter, which will be oriented towards potential obstacles regarding modern social media usage. The power of the citizen to choose what to consume and what kind of information best suits them is a welcome novelty but it also might confront us with problematic scenarios. In the rest of the paper, we would like to question some current practices within social media and focus our attention on the so-called power of the individual. What are the basic ideological trajectories of such assumptions? Putting aside the already mentioned "myth of us", the optimism of so-called empowered and well-informed citizens also has its roots in the developing technology and its potential for networking.

What is so exciting about social media platforms? What is the "novelty" occurring in social media? What projections are put into social media? Namely, social media are just communication channels, aren't they? The explanation for their popularity can be found in the process of networking, which is a basic organizational principle within social media. Within social media networking a great deal of power is transferred to ordinary people. They are in the centre of networks. They form their networks of affiliations and personal relationships within already established offline social networks; they also find other people to whom they connect, and they select information they regard as important for them. They have the power to present themselves on social media platforms (such as Facebook or Instagram) as they want to. It seems like we are living in a world perfectly fitted to ourselves. (Praprotnik, 2019: 124). But problems become clearer when we start asking unpleasant questions, such as: What types of motivations are brought to the front within social media? What types of communication acts are typical for social media? Do we enlarge our networks since we have an effective tool to go beyond our well-known social territory? Do we explore ourselves by using these networks? Have we broadened our symbolic and real world?

The answers can't be found in social media as technology. Instead of dealing with social media, we have to look more precisely at the very communication processes occurring within social media platforms. Certainly, each technology is an artefact which provides us with possibilities and opportunities. The materiality of our sociality is unquestionable and it is not a horror we have to escape from. Our "salvation" is not a kind of technology detox. Quite the contrary; we

have to acknowledge that technology is an infrastructure which is the elementary foundation of our relationships: Network connectivity functions as an infrastructure of intimacy - an infrastructure that is important for creating and maintaining relations, such as friendships or sexual encounters. Susanna Paasonen is quite clear about that: "Network connectivity functions as an affordance and resource without which individual and collective lives would no longer function in quite the same way. In fact, connectivity has grown into a matter of infrastructure that is reminiscent of electricity, gas or water supply, or heating. All kinds of mundane routines and connections with partners, friends and family are paced and facilitated by networked communications. Network connectivity functions as an infrastructure of intimacy that plays a key role in the creation and maintenance of friendships, sexual arrangements and affairs of the heart, as well as in the forging of their shapes and intensities. Intimacy, as discussed here, therefore refers not only to connections between people but to the networked environments in which these connections unfold and the connections that are formed through devices, apps and platforms: each of these aspects impacts on people, and people depend on them to live." (Paasonen, 2017). For Paasonen, intimacy does not simply refer to connections between individuals; rather, intimacy should be understood as the networked environments in which individuals' connections and relationships unfold. In other words, networked connections are sociotechnical affordances that modulate intimacy (Andreassen, Nebeling Petersen, Harrison, Raun, 2017: 10). Therefore, we should take material culture seriously in order to avoid simplistic interpretations of "what technology is going to do to us". This way we will be able to see the affordances and possibilities of technology and the constitutive side of technology for our everyday life: "What is critical today is not how machines might imitate human love - or how human love is no more thoughtful than a machine - but rather how human love already relies upon certain technical systems and devices to extend and define it. The human and the nonhuman are no longer so easily distinguished when technical devices are considered essential co-creators and makers of meaning that clearly participate in the evolution of the lifeworld." (Mackinnon, 2016: 7).

We have to be aware of the interdependence of technology and society and not consider technology as a (hostile, empowering...) "supplement" to society. We can find a quite similar analogy when considering the relationship between society and language

(discourse). Actual everyday discourse, be it in the media or between interlocutors, is not just a reflection of society, it is not a passive supplement “describing” a society. It is an active and constitutive element of society, because individuals (and society) can think, understand and “see” themselves only through discourse. In returning to modern apps and platforms we have to bear in mind that “social media should not be understood as distinct from our lives or as passive, preexisting channels through which we transmit ourselves and establish social connections; rather, social media are integrated parts of our lives. To paraphrase Deuze: we live in media, rather than with media (Deuze, 2011: 138). In the “culture of connectivity”, connections are determined as much by technology (through algorithms or platform architecture) as by users; thus, the meaning of ‘social’ in social media encompasses both human connectedness and automated connectivity (van Dijck, 2013: 11–12 in Nebeling Petersen, Harrison, Raun, Andreassen, 2017: 3). The ubiquity of media makes media “invisible”: “As media become pervasive and ubiquitous, forming the building blocks for our constant remix of the categories of everyday life (the public and the private, the local and the global, the individual and the collective), they become invisible – in the sense that, as Friedrich Kittler suggests, we become blind to that which shapes our lives the most.” (Deuze, 2011: 137). It is not a kind of pessimism; it is an acknowledgment of materiality of our lives: The potential power of people to shape their lives and identities can be found in the assumption that people produce themselves (and therefore each other) in media. This perhaps may additionally explain why people do not recognize their media habits because they are a constitutive part of them.” (Deuze, 2011: 138). We can conclude these considerations in a more condensed manner following Friedrich Kittler: “there are of course media technologies without love, but there is no love without media technologies.” (Kittler, 2010: 106).

Each technology has a certain kind of influence upon society but the extent of its influence is a result of the values and motivations of society. The technological opportunities are—theoretically speaking—quite huge, but we have to focus our attention towards existing practices within social media. Researchers Boyd and Ellison stress the following conclusions: “What makes social network sites unique is not that they allow individuals to meet strangers, but rather that they enable users to articulate and make visible their social networks. This can result in connections between individuals that

would not otherwise be made, but that is often not the goal, and these meetings are frequently between 'latent ties' who share some offline connection. On many of the large SNSs, participants are not necessarily 'networking' or looking to meet new people; instead, they are primarily communicating with people who are already a part of their extended social network" (Boyd, Ellison, 2008: 211). The distinctive feature of social media is that they are ego centric not topic centric. "Although we speak of 'social media', many contemporary social media platforms logic is quite individualistic. They are called Facebook, YouTube or MySpace and not WeBook, OurTube or OurSpace because they are all about the self-presentation of the individual (networked) self" (Fuchs, 2017: 36).

In line with this proclaimed personalization and me-oriented social media, we turn our bodies back to face the scene. We usually publish pictures of ourselves, our holiday images and so on. Our Facebook or Instagram publications go hand in hand with our already established offline and online presentations of ourselves. Our image of ourselves, our Facebook identity has constraints again. We have to act and communicate in a way that is consistent with our previous actions in order to remain a 'serious person'. Our Facebook visual and verbal presentations count as an index of our already established Facebook persona (Praprotnik, 2019: 125).

The critiques of social media optimism stress that "social media foster status-seeking behaviour and thereby promote the infiltration of marketing and advertising techniques into relationships and social behaviour". Alice Marwick, for example, exposes that "social media is predicated on the cultural logic of celebrity, according to which the highest value is given to mediation, visibility, and attention" (Marwick, 2013: 14 in Fuchs, 2017: 35–36). The existence of certain acts within the Facebook platform (for example, the sign I like) has itself formed an important frame of what is important and what the preferred communication acts within Facebook are. In line with this string of considerations, it is also an algorithmic power of social media, which was a starting point of Taina Bucher's approach to social media. Namely, influenced by Foucault's writings on Panopticism (the architectural structuring of visibility), Bucher argues for understanding the construction of visibility on Facebook through an architectural framework that pays particular attention to underlying software processes and algorithmic power. Through an analysis of EdgeRank, the algorithm structuring the flow of information and communication

on Facebook's 'News Feed', she argues that the regime of visibility constructed imposes a perceived "threat of invisibility" on the part of the participatory subject. As a result, she made a brilliant reversion of Foucault's notion of surveillance as a form of permanent visibility, arguing that participatory subjectivity is not constituted through the imposed threat of an all-seeing vision machine, but by the constant possibility of disappearing and becoming obsolete (Bucher, 2012: 1164). Let's see how she reformulates Foucault's notion of visibility: "In Facebook there is not so much a 'threat of visibility' as there is a 'threat of invisibility' that seems to govern the actions of its subjects. The problem as it appears is not the possibility of constantly being observed, but the possibility of constantly disappearing, of not being considered important enough. In order to appear, to become visible, one needs to follow a certain platform logic embedded in the architecture of Facebook." (Bucher, 2012: 1171).

Social media has become a serious business, and consequently, communication is not a kind of playful experimentation any more, as was the case in the late 20th century when people were communicating via anonymous Internet Relay Chat. Social media inhabitants are collecting a different kind of (social) capital in terms of likes, followers, etc. Likes become important, people are focused on collecting these signs. We might claim that "likes" as communication acts count as preferred responses (preferred seconds in conversational analysis). Accordingly, people often construct their publications in order to get such response. As Fuchs acknowledged: "The neoliberal logic of competition and individualism is expressed by the fact that on certain social media platforms, one accumulates likes, followers, friends or check-ins, and the more of it one has, the higher one's cultural online capital and social online capital" (Fuchs, 2017: 36). We can find similar logic focusing on improved visibility and constructed "importance" and impact on several platforms, even on those platforms with the motivation to be informative and not just to entertain. For example, the ResearchGate platform often informs and alerts profile owners to increase their impact stating: "Here are some suggestions to help you increase the impact of your research" (ResearchGate).

The already mentioned threat of invisibility is truly tightly inscribed into social media users' communication practices. Profiles within social media platforms are usually a well-crafted performance of carefully collected photographs which show our best version of us.

They are a similar kind of masquerade as those we can find in everyday self-representations. Namely, every type of our performances is a kind of intentional communication, therefore a kind of a masquerade deliberately crafted for the audience. Even our 'spontaneous' offline performances are to a great extent masquerades, because we have learnt through socialization scenarios of how to behave properly. So, we are on stage almost all the time. (Praprotnik, 2019: 126).

Conclusion: to network or to communicate; what would you prefer?

Social media platforms are usually described as serious, me-centred, personalized, networked, and interlinked spaces. Much weight is placed on visibility and influence. Is social media a friendly and encouraging environment for self-reflection? Is networking as an organizational principle successful for the development of more complex, reflective and all-encompassing relationships? What are our main communicative intentions when communicating through social media?

To be sure, every type of communication is a reflection of the social roles in which we appear and a reflection of the social practice we are performing at a specific moment. In presenting the right moves, gestures or words in certain situation we are signalling that we know the type of situation we are in. Every act of communication is therefore a constituent of a certain practice. Let's present Reckwitz' presentation of the practice we call "Romantic love": "The practice of falling in love with someone in the sense of 'Romantic love' for instance consists - as a culturally understandable practice - of a pattern of routinized (bodily) behaviour and of a certain way of understanding (oneself and another person). Single agents in their single mind/ bodies then - independent of one another - 'take over' the practice, and thus also its interpretative perspective. Yet, the knowledge that is a constitutive element of a practice is not only a way of understanding; it is - in connection with that - also a know-how and a certain way of wanting and feeling." (Reckwitz, 2002: 254).

While considering the relationship between communication and social practice we have to stress the "reverse" point of the same relationship too: communication constitutes social practice. Discourse is a reflective as well as a formative practice. In everyday life we constantly change our communication (=performance) according to the audience in front of us. So, what we are pointing

here at? The problem is the very environment (social media) which has integrated different social roles into one single profile. As Christian Fuchs stresses: "On social media such as Facebook, we act in various roles, but all of these roles become mapped onto single profiles that are observed by different people that are associated with our different social roles. This means that social media are social spaces, in which social roles tend to converge and become integrated in single profiles". (Fuchs, 2017: 50). We would like to explicate these quite important aspects by citing a slightly long but very informative and explanatory piece of another of Fuchs' articles: "Social media like Facebook are based on the creation of personal profiles that describe the various roles of a human being's life. In contemporary modern society, different social roles tend to converge in various social spaces. The boundaries between public life and private life as well as the work place and the home have become porous. As we have seen, Habermas identified systems (the economy, the state) and the lifeworld as central realms of modern society. The lifeworld can be further divided into culture and civil society. We act in different social roles in these spheres: for example as employees and consumers in the economic systems, as clients and citizens in the state system, as activists in the socio-political and in socio-economic spheres as lovers and consumers. We also act as family members in the private sphere, or as fan community members, parishioners, professional association members and so on in the socio-cultural sphere. A new form of liquid and porous sociality has emerged, in which we partly act in different social roles in the same social space." (Fuchs, 2017: 50).

Additionally, social media have quite a strong offline foundation and reflect our already established relationships. The offline and online world are not separated anymore. That is the reason why the "game" we are playing via social media has become so serious. Our Facebook or Instagram performances have to count as serious and interesting. Nevertheless, do we really want to be always serious and interesting? Or to put the problem another way: is it better to be "interesting" and in "good shape" or is it better to be "whole"? What would you prefer? (Praprotnik, 2019: 127). Our permanent availability and visibility results in a certain kind of connections: we have connections with lots of people within social media, but are we really connected to people? As Boyd and Ellison stress: "While their key technological features are fairly consistent, the cultures that emerge around SNSs are varied. Most sites support the maintenance of pre-

existing social networks, but others help strangers connect based on shared interests, political views, or activities” (Boyd, Ellison, 2008: 210). With social media, lots of people got a very useful type of technology which has enabled them to be in touch with their friends, classmates, and family members. But what about beyond that already known network? What are the possible problems when we build our everyday life within the same “old” network?

The cultural logic of visibility and prolongation of offline networks constitutes communication practices within social media to a great extent. Kate Hopkins states that “this type of almost constant communication between users has never been available to society in another way, and if anything intensifies the requirement for relationship building – we are now in each other’s spaces all the time” (Hopkins, 2014: 4). “Social media provide outlets for individuals who already have connections external to these media. They become users of this media to continue physical assemblies in an online environment, but in ways that seek to maximize attention. Where offline relationships simply migrate to social media, recent studies show that the primary forms of use and gratifications are maintaining a connection and an online presence, rather than exchanging information that is of any kind of educational, political or economic value” (Holmes, 2011: 105–106). This need for permanent visibility is a kind of reflection of a modern understanding of media. Let’s quote Nick Couldry: “... once the media (in any form) presents itself as the centre of society and we organise our lives and orient our daily rituals and practice towards it, we run the risk of falling prey to ‘the myth of the mediated centre’ (Couldry, 2003: 47 in Curran, Fenton, Freedman, 2012: 125). “Media rituals not only stress the significance of media but also allude to the importance of being “in the media” and of being able to communicate your message to others – whether this be for financial, political or social gain. The more powerful and influential you are, the better placed you are to get your message across. The Internet and social networking push this argument one step further. The millions of people who use social networking sites inhabit a mediated world that offers the possibility of more control than mainstream media, is mobile, interactive and holds endless creative potential, but is nonetheless mythic. The claimed ubiquity of the Internet and social media stresses the significance of always being tuned in and online. The seductive power of this mythic centre circulates around social life and serves to obscure the

reproduction of the dominant values of neoliberal society” (Curran, Fenton, Freedman, 2012: 125).

Finally, we would like to expose yet another already well-known process. Quite interestingly, it is a structural “derivation” of a much-highlighted characteristic of social media: personalization and the power to choose. Cultural and communication expectations are reinforced here, because social media enable community (or network) building on the basis of quite the same “taste”. Social media are effective tools for the prolongation of imagined communities and a place for gathering and circulation of individuals with the same political or cultural motivations and ideas. So, the question is whether social media enable an environment for better information exchange; do they encourage dissemination of information about important political, ecological, and educational problems? The answer once again lies in society; social media are just communication channels, a technology. As we said at the beginning: technology is not able to change us, technology is not able to save us – from ourselves. Networking at a theoretical level could be an ideal organizational principle for the networking of information and ideas; instead, we are faced with the networking of individuals. What is the consequence of having the power to choose what kind of information best suits my own interests?

In the introduction to his influential book *Republic: Divided Democracy in the Age of Social Media* (2017), Cass Sunstein referred to Nicholas Negroponte who “prophesied the emergence of ‘the Daily Me’. With the Daily Me, he suggested, you would not rely on the local newspaper to curate what you saw, and you could bypass the television networks. Instead, you could design a communication package just for you, with each component fully chosen in advance [...] What matters is that with the Daily Me, everyone could enjoy an architecture of control. Each of us would be fully in charge of what we see and hear” (Sunstein, 2017: 1).

Is that kind of power or “architecture of control” creative and refreshing in advance? We think the power to choose means also the power not to choose. If we are in full command of choosing what we read, listen to and hear, we are also in a position to avoid important information needed for full participation in everyday life. We already know the concept of homophily: a strong tendency to connect and bond with people who are like us. Within social media platforms

these processes can even be intensified. As Sunstein acknowledges: "... it is much too simple to say that any system of communication is desirable if and because it allows individuals to see and hear what they choose. Increased options are certainly good, and the rise of countless niches has many advantages. But unanticipated, unchosen exposures and shared experiences are important too" (Sunstein, 2017: 8). As Sunstein continues: "people should be free to choose. But freedom requires far more than that. It requires certain background conditions, enabling people to expand their own horizons and to learn what is true. [...] Real world interactions often force us to deal with diversity, whereas the virtual world may be more homogenous, not in demographic terms, but in terms of interest and outlook" (Putnam, 2000: 178, in Sunstein, 2017: 13). From the democratic point of view, the freedom to choose is a little problematic: "a system of free expression should not be seen solely in terms of consumers and consumption at all. In a free republic, such a system is designed to maintain the conditions for democratic self-government - to serve citizens, not only consumers" (Sunstein, 2017: 234). But, as usually happens, technology does not serve only for some anticipated positive scenarios. The use of technologies is a terrain where the real potentials, wisdoms, values and motivations of a society are fully expressed. Each use of technology is a reflection of the socio-cultural context. When analysing the "politics" of platforms and while suggesting possible solutions to improve moderation on social media platforms, Tarleton Gillespie has offered a straightforward and familiar explanation: "The dreams of the open web did not fail, exactly, nor were they empty promises to begin with. Many people put in a great deal of effort, time, resources, and dollars to pursue these dreams, and to build infrastructures to support them. But when you build a system that aspires to make possible a certain kind of social activity, even if envisioned in the most positive terms, you also make possible its inverse - activity that adopts the same shape in order to accomplish the opposite end. In embracing the Internet, the web, and especially social media platforms for public discourse and sociality, we made a Faustian bargain, or a series of them, and we are now facing the sober realities they produced. If we dreamed of free information, we found we also got free advertising. If we dreamed of participation, we also got harassment. If we dreamed of sharing, we also got piracy. If we dreamed of political activism online, we also got clicktivism, political pandering, and tweetstorms." (Gillespie, 2018: 204–205).

We can conclude once again that technology is a double-edged sword. We are faced with possibilities enabled by technologies as well as with actual much more diverse realizations. The freedom and power to choose what kind of information best suits me is not a road to “paradise”. The power to choose is also not the sole solution for developing a well-informed citizen. We would like to stress that it is of vital importance to be aware that we as individuals are not only consumers with special, often personalized interests, motivations and needs that have to be accomplished/fulfilled. We are at the same time citizens, too. And citizens usually have slightly broader interests and motivations. A citizen is not driven only in terms of consumption. A citizen’s motivations are more holistic; his motivations are not based only in terms of “my needs”, but in terms of “our needs” as a society. In a modern media-saturated world with vast opportunities, it is -paradoxically - of special importance to be well equipped with knowledge in order to fully understand the complexity of everyday life. Freedom demands responsibility and the ability to contextualize information. Nowadays, the responsibility of the individual for well-being is not smaller. The responsibility is bigger. We need media as well as all other literacies in order to be fully in command of our everyday life (Praprotnik, 2019: 131). And these considerations are turning us towards ourselves again. What is relevant for us, for society?

Our media environment is certainly very diverse. We are well equipped with smartphones and other devices which constantly deliver information to us. The materiality of our culture is a fact and our culture of communications and relationships is based upon material artefacts. What is important is to shift the focus from society as a landscape of consumers toward society as a landscape of citizens. How are we as a society looking at each other? More importantly: how are media discourse and corporations looking at us? For fully competent citizens it is important that we know what kind of information is relevant for us. And last but no less important, we have to revitalize the old-fashioned master idea of equality and ask ourselves how we can optimize technologies in order to develop and upgrade our society accordingly. Firstly, we have to be adequately equipped with certain knowledge and wisdom. If we turn once again back to Roszak, we do not need much more information, but we surely ought to have a certain passion for wisdom and knowledge.

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